

WHAT NATURE OF ARITHMETIC DIFFICULTIES DO STUDENTS WITH POOR SCHOLASTIC PERFORMANCE PRESENT IN SCHOOLS WITH AND WHAT IMPLICATIONS EMERGE?

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Abstract

Poor scholastic performance is a common problem faced by children, and is a challenge to students, their teachers, and parents. While the professional literature abounds with investigations of the various factors that cause poor scholastic performance in school-going children, the nature of academic or basic skill difficulties seen in such children have not been appraised. Of all the factors that are affected in a child who is experiencing poor scholastic performance, it can be safely assumed that quite a large number among them would have difficulties in basic arithmetic skills and operations. What arithmetic skill and operational deficits would these children pose as a challenge to both learn and teach? This study was conceived to see if we can identify the nature of academic skill deficits in these children and what specific implications emerge for their teachers. A purposive sample (n=72) limited to students with poor scholastic performance attending a city-based school from class 8 to 12, following the National Open School Curriculum, was selected for this study. Their performance on a criterion-referenced assessment tool was analyzed using statistical methods and it was found that there existed a significant difference in the mean marks of students in class 8 to class 12.

Keywords : *Scholastic backwardness, arithmetic difficulties, open school, learning disability, statistical data processing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

A low level of achievement in math in schools is a concern for most nations (Gersten, 2009). Ask any child what subject they learn in school with aversion, the chances are that most of them would say math (Scholz et al, 2008).

Approximately 5-9% of students may be identified with mathematics disability (e.g., Badian, 1983; Geary, 2004; Fleischner & Manheimer, 1997). Comparable prevalence was documented in Jordan as well (McBride, 2007). Though an upsurge in research in arithmetic disabilities started as long as the 1970s in most parts of the world, interest in learning disabilities in arithmetic have traditionally received less attention than other academic areas in our country (Kaur, Kohli, & Devi, 2008).

It is not uncommon that many students begin secondary school with a poor understanding of the structure of arithmetic (Warren & Cooper, 2009). Inefficient use of strategies, error-prone approaches, time taken in mental computations all have been implicated for this (Bezuk & Cegelka, 1995; Pegg & Graham, 2007). Likewise, math difficulties are encountered by college students too (McGlaughlin, Knoop, & Holliday, 2005) though there is little available in literature as to the nature of difficulties experienced by them (Strawser & Miller, 2001; Zawaisa & Gerber, 1993).

Maya et. al/ What Nature of Arithmetic Difficulties Do Students with Poor Scholastic Performance Present in Schools With and What Implications Emerge?

A difficulty in learning mathematics is an often seen feature of poor scholastic performance, of which many are those with a learning disability and/or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Lindsay et al, 2001). In a school-based study, it was found that no student who was delayed more than six months in mathematics in sixth grade ever caught up, and another study has shown persistence of severe arithmetic disorder in half of affected pre-teen children (Mazzocco et.al, 2003). In a study of gifted high school students, Abu-Hamour (2013) found that math achievement and not language achievement may be used with confidence to classify gifted students; high achiever had higher mean scores than moderate and low achievers on all study variables; intrinsic motivation then extrinsic motivation had the highest correlation with math achievement and can be used to differentiate males and females performance.

2. METHODS

2.1 Sample

From a population of 120 students with poor scholastic performance, a sample of 72 was selected. The sample consisted of students from class 8 to class12 as shown in Table 1.

Table1: Sample Description

Class	No. of Girls	No. of Boys	Total
8	4	4	8
9	4	18	22
10	4	9	13
11	4	17	21
12	3	5	8
Total	19	53	72

2.2 Measures

Following tool was administered to collect data on math performance of the sample:
The Informal Test of Arithmetic and Math Skills (*i*-TOAMS)

The *i*-TOAMS (Ajit, 2012) was developed at the school where the sample was taken and is extensively used as criterion-referenced tool in identifying children with arithmetic and mathematic difficulties. The tool consists of two parts: A – Arithmetical Skills and B – Mathematical Skills. Only the Part A was used for the present study which included the following subtests: number identification, number writing, missing number, place values, addition, subtraction, and multiplication (single digit, single digit with regrouping, double digit, double digit with regrouping, multi digit, and multi digit with regrouping), division (without remainder and with remainder), fractions, decimals, percentages, and word problems. The test consisted of 124 items on basic arithmetic operations. The questions were from the regular school math curriculum of class1 to class5. Error analysis was done to identify the nature of errors exhibited: incorrect operation, incorrect number facts, random error, incorrect algorithm, regrouping error, process substitution, omission, directional, and placement.

2.3 Procedure

The school where the sample was located was approached for the purpose of the study. Permission was sought from authors three and four for data collection; they were also inducted as co-authors of the study. Data for the purpose of study was taken from the school with the consent of parents of the students. The Part A of *i*-TOAMS was administered on an afternoon by their class teachers under the supervision of the fourth author. The test answer sheets were then analyzed in detail by the first and second author.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) which was used to calculate ANOVA. Multiple Comparison Tables (to show which group differed from each other) and Box Plot were used too. Data is also presented in frequency, percentages, and graphical forms.

3. RESULTS

A total of 72 students with poor scholastic performance were identified from 120 students present in a school for these children in Cochin. The students were between the age group of 13 to 18 years. 48 students had to be excluded as they were absent on the day the test was scheduled and given.

Table 2: Range of Scores in Percentage

Marks in %	No. of Students
0 – 25	5
25 – 50	17
50 – 75	25
75 – 100	25

Table 2 shows the range of scores in percentage obtained by the students in the test. The marks of each student out of 124 were converted to percentage. The marks in percentage were then classified into classes of equal intervals and the number of students under these classes is depicted in the table.

It can be seen from the table that 69% (50 out of 72 students) of students have scored more than 50% of the aggregate score. Compared to other classes, the students of class 8 showed poor performance. This may mean that their knowledge level is perhaps equivalent to the knowledge level of students in class 1 and 2 of a regular school.

Table 3: Mean Marks in Percentage

Class	No. of Students	Minimum Mark	Maximum Mark	Mean Mark	Mean %
Class 8	8	30	94	64.25	51.8
Class 9	22	0	113	60.41	48.7
Class 10	13	48	109	85.23	71.2
Class 11	21	12	116	79.48	65.6
Class 12	8	102	120	110.50	89.1

The Mean percentage of marks in each class is shown in Table 3. All 12th class students scored more than 89% in the test. Compared to other classes 12th class students showed better performance. However, errors were seen in subtests of fractions and decimals. It was also observed that the mean percentage of marks increased from class 8 to class 12 except for class 9 which could be due to the poor performance of one child who scored 0 marks.

Quantitative analysis based on difficult questions (higher level task) on each arithmetic skill i.e., Double Digit With Regrouping and Multi Digit With Regrouping (+, -, x, /) was conducted only for 8th to 11th classes, since 12th have performed well.

Table 4 shows the error analysis in percentage; error analysis was done on the basis of errors committed. In each of the above higher level tasks, there were five items. Even if there was a minimum of one error in the set of 5 items, it was counted as an error.

Table 4: Errors in Percentage

Maya et. al/ What Nature of Arithmetic Difficulties Do Students with Poor Scholastic Performance Present in Schools With and What Implications Emerge?

Arithmetic Skills		Class 8	Class 9	Class 10	Class 11
Addition	DDWR	50	36	46	45
	MDWR	63	68	62	50
Subtraction	DDWR	88	77	54	50
	DWR	100	86	69	68
Multiplication	DDWR	75	86	77	82
	MDWR	100	100	100	95
Division	WR	88	91	100	82
Fraction		100	95	100	91
Decimal		100	95	100	100
Percentage		100	100	100	86
Word problems		100	100	100	91

Statistical Data Processing

The data were analyzed in software statistical package SPSS 17.0. We performed descriptive statistics for the total test and ANOVA to determine inter-group differences.

To determine whether there are any significant differences between the independent groups ANOVA is used. For One-Way ANOVA, H_0 was taken as "Arithmetic skill is same in each class" and H_1 as "At least one class differs in their arithmetic skill".

Table 5: One-way ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17321.414	4	4330.353	6.882	.000
Within Groups	42160.364	67	629.259		
Total	59481.778	71			

Table 5 shows the output of ANOVA analysis and whether we have a statistically significant difference between the means of class 8 to class12. It can be seen that the significance level is 0 ($p=0$) which is below 0.05 and therefore there is a significant difference in the mean marks of students in class 8 to class12. This means that there are significant differences between the classes as a whole as far as math achievement is concerned.

Table 6 shows which classes differed from each other using a multiple comparison table. We can see that there is a significant difference between class8 and class 12 ($p=0.004$), class9 and class10 ($p=0.047$), class9 and class12 (0.0), and class 11 and class12 (0.032) at 5% level of significance.

Figure 1 shows the data on a Box Plot. The black middle line in each box represents the median for each data set. The first and third quartile is the edges of the boxes which are known as the inter quartile range (IQR). The extreme values are the ends of the lines extending from the IQR. Points at a greater distance from the median than 1.5 times the IQR are shown in small circles which are called outliers. 33rd and 63rd students in the sample are the outliers in class10; 32nd student in the sample is the outlier in class 11; 67th and 72nd students in the sample is the outliers in class12.

Table6: Multiple Comparison table

(I) class	(J) class	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
8	9	3.841	10.357	.996	-25.19	32.88
	10	-20.981	11.272	.348	-52.58	10.62
	11	-15.226	10.422	.591	-44.44	13.99
	12	-46.250*	12.543	.004	-81.41	-11.09
9	8	-3.841	10.357	.996	-32.88	25.19
	10	-24.822*	8.775	.047	-49.42	-.22
	11	-19.067	7.653	.105	-40.52	2.39
	12	-50.091*	10.357	.000	-79.13	-21.06
10	8	20.981	11.272	.348	-10.62	52.58
	9	24.822*	8.775	.047	.22	49.42
	11	5.755	8.853	.966	-19.06	30.57
	12	-25.269	11.272	.177	-56.87	6.33
11	8	15.226	10.422	.591	-13.99	44.44
	9	19.067	7.653	.105	-2.39	40.52
	10	-5.755	8.853	.966	-30.57	19.06
	12	-31.024*	10.422	.032	-60.24	-1.81
12	8	46.250*	12.543	.004	11.09	81.41
	9	50.091*	10.357	.000	21.06	79.13
	10	25.269	11.272	.177	-6.33	56.87
	11	31.024*	10.422	.032	1.81	60.24

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Fig 1: Box Plot

4. DISCUSSION

Maya et. al/ What Nature of Arithmetic Difficulties Do Students with Poor Scholastic Performance Present in Schools With and What Implications Emerge?

The following observations are based on the test results. It can be seen Table 2 that 70% of students have scored more than 50% of aggregate score. Likewise, it is evident from Table 3 that all the 12th grade students have scored more than 89% but with a few errors in fractions and decimals. It is also clear from Table 4 that the students of class 8 to 11 face difficulty in interpreting, analyzing and solving multiple digit multiplication, division, fraction, decimal, percentage and word problems compared to addition, subtraction and multiplication (SDWR & DDWR); these items are at class 3 to 5 level in a regular school math curriculum.

It is seen that in all classes the errors are minimum in addition and subtraction (class 1 level) compared to other tasks. In class 8, majority of students did not attend the last part of the test: fractions, decimals, percentage, and word problems. Many of them have made errors in higher tasks of division. Class 9 students have attended the word problems but many of them were not thorough with the concepts of fraction, decimal and percentage. In class 10, few students had not attended the items like fraction, decimal, percentage while the rest had all made maximum errors in these tasks. In class 11, maximum errors were observed in fraction, decimal and percentage.

We can conclude that the students of class 8 to class 11 have not reached the standard of their typical peers; most are only at class 4 level or below. We have also observed that there is a significant difference in the arithmetic skill of students in class 8 and class 12, class 9 and class 10, class 9 and class 12, and class 11 and class 12.

5. IMPLICATIONS

Many adolescent students begin secondary school with a poor understanding of the structure of arithmetic (Warren & Cooper, 2009). While past researchers have focused on identification and remediation of students with MD in elementary and secondary grades, there is indeed a growing need to study the nature of these difficulties that impact postsecondary education (McGlaughlin, Knoop, & Holliday, 2005) and found deficits in working memory, math fluency, reading comprehension, and visual/spatial/nonverbal ability weaknesses as the most significant factors.

Children require to be actively learning mathematics to offset the adverse effects of failure and frustration in learning math (Clark, 2007). Explicit and systematic instruction that includes providing models of proficient problem solving, verbalization of thought processes, guided practice, corrective feedback, and frequent cumulative review; materials that promote visual representations of math ideas; building of fluent retrieval of basic arithmetic facts, and authentic projects (Gersten et al, 2009 & Banchoff, 2000). Manipulative that can be touched, moved about, rearranged, and otherwise handled by students are an excellent way of engaging students in math (Kennedy, 1986). Kaur, Kohli, & Devi (2008) report the efficacy of multimedia; cognitive strategies; and eclectic approach in enhancing the mathematical achievement or performance of learning disabled children.

The present study indicates the need to teach and prepare students with difficulty in learning mathematics the basic arithmetic operations that have both functional and possible future use in terms of learning accountancy which involves basic math operations.

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